

Standalone modular powerplant with parabolic-trough collectors combined with an organic Rankine cycle (S-ORC)

Fernando Inti Leal*

Institute of Energy and Environment of the University of São Paulo (IEE-USP), Av. Prof. Luciano Gualberto, 1289, São Paulo, SP, Brazil.

Abstract

The present study designs and analyzes the performance of a modular standalone small-scale and self-sustaining electricity generating plant. This plant is composed of a thermal fluid circuit that absorbs heat from a solar source using a solar parabolic-trough collector (PTC) combined with an Organic Rankine Cycle (S-ORC). The thermodynamic model of the PTC is developed to operate a 15kW micro steam turbine, generating 13.7kW net power output daily, ranging from 90kWh to 110kWh. Rejected heat from the condensate is used to meet thermal demand using a 0.5 HP water pump, delivering around 27 l/min of 57 °C heated water. S-ORC facilities using low-impact chlorofluoromethane derivatives have been shown to deliver solid performance with an overall efficiency of 17.29%, making them a compelling option. The S-ORC system's deployment in standalone modules for both thermal and solar sides highlights its potential as an alternative to crystalline silicon photovoltaic cells in specific scenarios. The capital expenditure for the small-sized S-ORC facility is estimated at around \$2,003 per kWe. Finally, the calculated Levelized Cost of Electricity of \$0.135/kWh and internal rate of return of 22.7% for the project's twenty-year lifetime is competitive when compared to other concentrating solar power projects or small rooftop PV systems' price range, especially considering the additional thermal heat provided.

1. Introduction

THE need for small-scale and self-sustaining solar thermal combined heat and power (CHP) power systems has motivated some studies in this field of research, especially with the growing demand for decentralised electricity supply in areas poorly served by electricity grids. In Brazil, some isolated areas in the Amazon or in the northeast of the country, located mainly in rural or indigenous areas, are still outside the National Interconnected System (SIN). The global access deficit, defined as the proportion of the global population lacking electricity in their houses or cities, has decreased from 1.22 billion in 2010 to 759 million in 2019. This decline is predominantly driven by a reduction in the number of people living without electricity in sub-Saharan Africa, accounting for over three-quarters of the total decrease. Over the past decade, there has been an increase in the percentage of people with access to electricity, rising from 83% in 2010 to 90% in 2019, representing an average annual electrification rate of 0.876%.

However, it is estimated that as many as 660 million people may still be without electricity worldwide by 2030 [1]. In 2023, Brazil's electricity distribution network had an installed capacity of 209,102 MW, reaching 179,311 km in extension, with a projected increase of almost 26% in its total length by 2027 [2]. The micro and mini distributed generation, incentivised by the introduction of the net metering system by ANEEL Resolution nº 482 of 2012, reached an installed capacity of 22,370 MW. The region selected for the calculation and sizing of the most relevant system's equipment was one belonging to the semiarid zone of the State of Piauí, where in some cities over half the houses (55.3%) still lack access to electricity grids for basic daily life, schools, or small hospitals [3]. This is also the region of the National Park Serra da Capivara, considered to be world heritage site in 1991 by UNESCO and a touristic place and conservation institute created in 1979 with the intent to protect a vast archaeological site, which has a huge variety of prehistoric vestiges and paintings, visited annually by tourists, archaeologists, and researchers from many different countries.

In this context, the objective of the study was not to innovate in terms of design, but rather to summarise theoretical and thermodynamics calculations and steps to develop a sustainable and renewable small-scale power system to supply remote areas, especially those where solar radiation is intense, with a reliable and self-sustainable facility, employing a parabolic-trough solar collector (PTC).

While previous studies have analysed the thermodynamic performance of parabolic trough collectors (PTCs) in solar thermal applications, many have primarily focused on large-scale power generation or hybrid systems, often overlooking small-scale, modular, and standalone implementations. Research on integrating PTCs with Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) systems has emphasised theoretical efficiency improvements without addressing practical deployment challenges, cost-effectiveness, or auxiliary thermal benefits.

The present study bridges these gaps by designing and evaluating a self-sustaining, small-scale electricity generation system utilizing a PTC-driven S-ORC. Unlike previous works, this study not only develops a thermodynamic model tailored for a 15kW micro steam turbine but also quantifies its economic feasibility, energy output, and thermal co-generation potential. The modular nature of the proposed system enhances its adaptability, positioning it as a viable alternative to conventional photovoltaic solutions, particularly in scenarios where both electrical and thermal energy demands must be met efficiently.

In this sense, the PTC absorbs solar energy, which is then used to heat a thermal fluid. This, in turn, vaporizes a chosen organic fluid, thereby generating power from a micro steam turbine with an approximate net power output of 15kW. An ORC is an effective means of generating power from thermal energy, and it can also utilise a variety of heat sources, including solar collectors, geothermal energy, waste, and process heat. Parabolic-trough solar power plants are currently among the most mature technologies for solar thermal power production.

A PTC is a linear-focus solar collector that absorbs energy from the sun and converts it into useful thermal energy in the heat transfer fluid (HTF), which circulates through the solar field. It is basically composed of a parabolic-trough-shaped solar concentrator that reflects direct solar radiation onto a receiver tube located in the focal line of the parabola. Once the geometry of the PTC and the thermal properties of the HTF have been defined, system performance and energy gained by the HTF can be calculated for different setups. PTCs are typically operated at temperatures of up to 400°C and synthetic oil is commonly used as HTF [4].

The Solar Organic Rankine Cycle (S-ORC) has been the subject of theoretical and practical studies since the 1970s. Initial research reported overall efficiencies ranging from 3.0 to 7.0%, however, recent studies have documented significantly higher efficiencies, ranging from 15.0 to 25.0%. Recent experimental studies on low-scale power plants (up to 10 kW) have typically employed vane or scroll expanders, as evidenced in [5]. This study examined an analogous system to the one proposed, operating on one- or two-stage expansion of R245fa, utilising modified commercial HVAC compressors. Additionally, an attempt was made to assess the performance of n-pentane and R134a. Although R134a was found to demonstrate satisfactory performance in the aforementioned study, it was ultimately excluded from the scope of this research due to its notably low critical temperature, which is incompatible with the targeted optimal operating ORC temperature of $T_{op}=120^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The software-assisted evaluation analysis performed by [6] sought to identify the optimal design point, turbine pressure, and evaporator temperature to ensure optimal performance. The study demonstrated that, under optimal theoretical conditions, benzene emerged as the superior working fluid, achieving efficiencies of up to 24.17% when utilising both a superheater and a recuperator. In a large-scale case study, Jaramillo et al. [7] established that the energy and exergy efficiencies of the S-ORC power plant decrease as the incident solar radiation increases. To overcome this issue, they proposed the use of additional storage technologies. Molten salts have been identified as a means of significantly enhancing the solar fraction [7, 29], though it should be noted that they are considerably more expensive than conventional thermal fluids. Consequently, they are better suited to large solar heliostat facilities, such as the Ivanpah Solar Electric Generating System in California. This option was not considered in the present research.

Another theoretical analysis was conducted by [8], in which the thermal energy required by a S-ORC is supplied by stationary solar collectors. They analysed several fluids and operating conditions to propose interesting insights about the choice and sizing of the equipment, such as the importance of the solar cycle setup and several parameters for other organic fluids. In a separate study, Shahverdi et al. [9] investigated different ORC working fluids in S-ORC systems. Their results, which were validated with experimental results, revealed that R113 at saturated condition in an Archimedes screw turbine (AST) inlet gave the highest ORC net power. However, due to its high Ozone Depleting Potential (ODP), R113 is likely to be prohibited in an increasing number of countries, so it was not considered for the purpose of this study. Another interesting approach was made by [10] who presented a numerical and real-time performance analysis of PTC system designed for solar air-conditioning applications of around 3 kW. Then, an experimental PTC system setup is established with a concentration ratio of 9.93 using evacuated tube receivers.

2. Methods

In the initial phase of any design, it is imperative to identify a suitable power generator expander that functions within the range of small pressures and temperatures [5, 11]. This has resulted in the development of small, lightweight steam turbines or scroll expanders, which are capable of delivering heat and electricity with a relatively high efficiency. One notable piece of equipment is the Twin Turbine [12], which has been constructed on a commercial scale in a modular unit. This approach serves to reduce the overall cost of the project and enhance its feasibility. Another salient aspect pertains to the capacity to modulate such turbines to vary the final output, a capability enabled by their six nozzles, each of which is capable of delivering up to 2.5 kWe. Consequently, the six nozzles would account for the gross output desired in this study. The microturbine inlet conditions consist of superheated steam at pressures ranging from 10.5 to 12 bar, with a design speed of 26,000 rpm and a power output of 3 phase AV 860 Hz, subsequent to rectification [12]. Furthermore, the properties of the designated working fluids significantly influence the performance of the ORC cycle [13]. As previously mentioned in [14], the appropriate thermodynamic properties can result in higher cycle performance and lower costs. In order to achieve a successful ORC-Solar integrated cycle, it is recommended that the ideal organic working fluid should have the following characteristics: high molecular weight; small heat content, meaning a low enthalpy to vaporize; high critical pressure and temperature, to allow cycle operating temperature to absorb most of the solar heat available, up to that temperature.

The selection of an organic fluid is predicated on the premise that, in contrast to water, it engenders diminished operating pressures, thereby mitigating the risk of explosion or failure of pipelines and equipment. Additionally, the enthalpy and latent heat of water are elevated, necessitating substantially larger solar fields to generate saturated or marginally superheated steam at the turbine inlet. Additionally, the organic fluid must be relatively cheap and found in commercial scale, to avoid a high system cost, as well as non-flammable, non-corrosive, non-toxic and, when referring to chlorine or fluorine refrigerants, very low environmental impact, meaning their Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP) and Global Warming Potential (GWP) must be as minimal as possible.

Among the pre-selected fluids, the one which presented the best congregation of most positive aspects and chosen for simulation was the R-123 or 2,2-Dichloro-1,1,1-trifluoroethane [13,15], which is a HCFC retrofit refrigerant created to replace R-11. It is predominantly employed in low-pressure centrifugal chillers, exhibiting a minimal ozone-depleting potential and a low greenhouse gas impact. An alternative equivalent substitute for R-123 is HFO-1233zd(E) or (E)-1-Chloro-3,3,3-trifluoroprop-1-ene, a more recent organic refrigerant. While the thermodynamic properties of R-123 are relatively close, HFO-1233zd(E) offers enhanced environmental and safety profiles, with comparable or marginally superior efficiency in many applications. It is widely regarded as the optimal replacement for R-123 in centrifugal chillers and analogous systems, although it is around 40% more expensive than R-123 [28].

It is important to acknowledge the challenges associated with the use of thermofluids and heat transfer fluids in concentrating solar power (CSP) units. These challenges are both technical and economic, and are more likely to arise in larger-scale plants. The corrosive nature of these fluids and their high temperatures can lead to damage, potentially reducing their lifespan and compromising their thermal stability over time. The management of material compatibility can be challenging, and fluid deterioration can result in

diminished productivity [29]. Consequently, ensuring material compatibility becomes paramount in combating corrosion and associated issues. With regard to the thermal heat-absorbing cycle, the selected fluid must exhibit specific characteristics, such as being commercially available due to cost considerations, as well as being stable under the desired operating conditions. The selection of a thermal fluid for heat transfer to a process is also contingent on the temperature and pressure conditions that affect the HTF, given that its viscosity must remain low within the operational temperature

range (120 – 200° C) to ensure optimal heat transfer efficiency [13,14,16].

Furthermore, as with the organic refrigerant, it is essential that the fluid possesses a relatively high specific heat and is non-corrosive to common metals and alloys. This ensures compatibility with most heat transfer systems and evaporators, avoiding the necessity for specific alloys and materials, which would otherwise increase the cost and complexity of the project for a small-scale unit.

FIGURE 1. Overall view of cycle detailed with equipment and respective connections

The chosen thermal fluid for the solar side cycle is Dowtherm Q Heat Transfer Fluid, which contains a mixture of diphenyl ethane and alkylated aromatics. Compared to hot oils, it exhibits better thermal stability, particularly at the upper end of the hot phase user range, and significantly better low temperature pumpability. It is notable that the fluid demonstrates adequate thermal stability at temperatures of up to 330°C, and it fulfils the criteria to function as the heat transfer fluid from the solar collector to the organic fluid power cycle. This fluid is commercially available [17]. As demonstrated in Fig. 1, the overall circuit is based on a regular ORC with a counter-current heat recuperator. The total gross output of 15 kWe is comprised of six 2.5kW turbine nozzles. Copper-brazed plate heat exchangers find application in the medium pressure heat transfer (1,200 kPa) and regular condensate recirculation pump contexts. For the entire circuit to function, as demonstrated in Fig.2, thermal oil calculated mass flow rate was of about 2,430.5 kg/h. That means roughly 2.82 m³/h due to a density of about 860 kg/m³, at the mean operating temperature at the steady state flow of T=155°C.

FIGURE 2. Temperature Distribution in the Steam Generator at steady flow

$$h_e - h_s = - \int_e^s v dP \quad (5)$$

3. Materials and Conditions

In the context of the solar cycle, the system incorporates a thermal storage tank with a capacity of 6.0 m³, equipped with thermal buffering. This configuration is designed to ensure sufficient storage capacity, with its volume being double that required to accommodate the hourly flow rate. The tank is encased within a packed bed of 50 mm glass wool, a measure implemented to mitigate the risk of sudden temperature fluctuations during the day, caused by variations in solar irradiation. Additionally, the system utilises a thermal fluid gear pump. The approximate tank volume estimate was confirmed through the application of the equation outlined in [7]. Volume of the tank can be calculated by:

$$V_{tank} = \frac{E_{stored}}{\rho_{oil} C_p \Delta T} \quad (1)$$

In the proposed arrangement, it is stipulated that all three cycle heat exchangers (i.e. evaporator, recuperator, and condenser) are to be dimensioned in order to obtain the imposed minimum pinch point of 5°C, as illustrated in Figure 2, and pressure drop according to the pump specifications (see Table 2). For the evaporator thermal design, calculations were performed for a double pipe heat exchanger using Churchill's, Colebrook's, and Fanning's Equations, as well as Gnielinksi's Correlation. In this sense the general governing equation is:

$$q = UA \frac{\Delta T_a - \Delta T_b}{\ln \left(\frac{\Delta T_a}{\Delta T_b} \right)} \quad (2)$$

The calculations were performed using the Thermal Design of Double Pipe Heat Exchangers spreadsheet calculator, developed by ASME/McGraw Hill. It is recommended that R-123 be condensed in an air condenser in order to avoid unnecessary water consumption, if necessary, given that the proposed cycle is intended to operate in a dry land, semiarid region. However, if water is available or if there is a need to address thermal demand at a hotel or facility, for example, the condensate rejected heat could be utilised for this purpose.

Small PTCs represent the CSP system technology with the highest potential for such thermal demand. The most common cogeneration applications that require thermal energy at high temperatures are industrial process heat production, heat-driven refrigeration, and low-temperature heat demand with high consumption rates (e.g., domestic hot water, space heating, swimming pool heating, pumping, irrigation water and desalination) [18].

In this instance, the range of desired flow rates for the secondary heated water, which can reach temperatures of up to 100°C, is selected in order to satisfy the required temperature: $\Delta T_n = \frac{15.23}{\dot{m}}$. As such, the use of a small ½ HP water pump in the project, would deliver around 27 l/min of 56.8 °C heated water, considering regular water inlet supply at 23 °C.

In order to perform thermodynamic balances, the First and Second Laws of Thermodynamics were applied to each control volume surrounding the cycle's equipment. The main hypotheses assumed for the obtained results were that the entire system operated in a steady state at an optimal level, and that there were no mass fluctuations over time. Furthermore, the variations in gravitational and kinetic energy between the entrance and exit points for each control volume were negligible. The following results were obtained:

$$\dot{Q}_{CV} + \dot{m}(h_e - h_s) = \dot{W}_{CV} \quad (3)$$

$$s_s = s_e + \int_e^s \frac{\delta q}{T} + s_{ger} \quad (4)$$

As for the pumps the relation applied is shown in equation 5, where index *e* refers to entrance and *s* to exit of control volume:

The PTC is composed of a concentrator, a receiver tube, a glass cover tube, and a one-direction tracking system, with incoming solar radiation concentrated at the focal line of the PTC, where the receiver tube is situated and the HTF flowing inside absorbs the concentrated solar heat flux. The thermal design of the proposed system is based on calculations of trough focal point and concentration ratio. The characteristics of the PTC evacuated tube receiver are also calculated in terms of heat loss coefficient, radiation coefficient, overall heat transfer coefficient, and useful heat gain.

According to [19], the 2020 value of average daily solar irradiation in the horizontal level was of $I_b = 5.90$ kWh/m² day, up to 6.61 kWh/m² day in September, for the measuring station of São Raimundo Nonato, the closest to the selected area. The location coordinates are: 09°00'54''S e 42°41'56''O, therefore latitude angle of $\Phi = -9.0054^\circ$. To calculate the best tracking system for the solar collector, if used, geometry parameters were calculated for the June the 21st and December the 21st, respectively winter and summer solstice in southern hemisphere, both at selected time 11:00AM. Initially the solar declination was found to be:

$$\delta = 23.45 \cdot \text{sen} \left(360 \cdot \frac{284 + N}{365} \right) \quad (6)$$

The Zenith angle can be calculated according to:

$$\cos \theta_z = \cos \Phi \cos \delta \cos \omega + \text{sen} \Phi \text{sen} \delta \quad (7)$$

For the tracking solution that would minimize the incidence angle, two arrangements were possible, a Horizontal East-West or North-South Rotation Axis, both with continuous adjustment to minimize the referred angle. For the first case being E-W:

$$\cos \theta = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \delta \text{sen}^2 \omega} \quad (8)$$

And for the second case N-S:

$$\cos \theta = \sqrt{\cos^2 \theta_z + \cos^2 \delta \text{sen}^2 \omega} \quad (9)$$

In mid-March and September, we notice that δ approaches 0°. This way, due the characteristics of the region, the solar parameters involved, and other variables, the calculated optimal angles of incidence vary from 13.73° to 15.00°, while the most favourable tracking system for the project would be a Horizontal East-West Rotation Axis, with variable surface inclination β given by [20, 21]: $\text{tg} \beta = \text{tg} \theta_z |\cos \gamma_s|$ (10)

For a linear concentrator system, the useful heat gain in the collector can be given as [20]:

$$Q_u = F_R A_a [G_b n_0 - \frac{A_r}{A_a} U_L (T_i - T_a)] \quad (11)$$

Being F_R the collector heat removal factor, n_0 is the collector optical efficiency, and G_b is the beam (or direct) irradiation.

The global heat losses due to convection, radiation and thermal conduction in (W/m²C) can be calculated as:

$$U_L = h_w + h_r + U_{cond} \quad (12)$$

$$h_w = \frac{Nu \cdot k}{l} \quad (13)$$

While Nu is the Nusselt Number, dependent on the Reynolds Number calculated for the external air flow. Also, $h_r = 4\sigma \varepsilon T^3$ (14). Being σ the Stefan-Boltzmann constant of 5.67037×10^{-8} W/m²K⁴, and

ϵ the emissivity of the absorber and envelope. The considered values for these specific parameters are detailed at Tables 1 and 2. Finally, the energetic balance applied to the control volume around the solar collector gives the exit thermal fluid temperature as:

$$T_o = T_i + \frac{Q_u}{\dot{m} \cdot C_p} \quad (15)$$

In a CSP, solar radiation is incident on the collector surface, called aperture area A_a , and this radiation is reflected or redirected into a smaller receiver area A_r . The concentration factor is defined as: $CR = \frac{A_a}{A_r}$ (16). In order to have an appropriate thermal size for the solar field and the nominal Rankine cycle thermal power, it is necessary to set a design point in which solar field performance is nominal. In this case, value of average daily solar irradiation in the horizontal level was of $\bar{I}_{av} = 6.2 \text{ kWh/m}^2\text{day}$ in July.

A polished stainless-steel sheet 304 ASTM of 0.5 mm is used as a reflector medium for each trough. In this case, the dimensions of the individual collector unit are of $3.0\text{m} \times 1.5 \text{ m}$. The sheet is bent to achieve the desired designed concentration ratio of 9.9 and focal point 0.210m. The PTC was chosen as the closest available prototype for designing the solar field [10, 22].

The absorber tube must exhibit high resistance to corrosion, low thermal expansion, and high thermal conductivity. Such characteristics are exhibited by copper, which is both malleable and relatively inexpensive. The cover glass must be made of a material with high transmittance, low reflectance, and low refractive index, in order to transmit the maximum amount of the incident radiation reflected from the mirrors. The reflector is constituted of a 0.5 mm-thick aluminium sheet with a special solar coating, MiroSun by Alanod Solar [23]. The absorber tube is composed of copper with a selective coating of black chrome, manufactured by [24]. The inner diameter of the absorber pipe is 30 mm, and the other parameters of the collector system were obtained from the reference literature.

Table 1 – PTC's overall parameters and calculation results

Parameter	Description	Value
$\rho_{concentrator}$	Concentrator reflectivity	0.93
CR	Concentration ratio	9.93
FP	Focal point	0.21 m
F_R	Heat removal factor	0.85
τ	Envelope transmissivity	0.96
α	Coating absorptivity	0.95
D_1	Absorber tube outer diameter	32 mm
D_2	Absorber tube inner diameter	30 mm
D_3	Envelope outer diameter	120 mm
D_4	Envelope inner diameter	118 mm
L1	Effective collector length	3.00 m
L2	Collector width	1.50 m
η_0	Optical efficiency	0.85
η_c	Collector efficiency	0.69
N	Number of collectors	60
A_a	Calculated Total Collector Area	270.0 m ²
$K_{\gamma\tau\alpha\psi}$	Modifier incidence angle x interception factor	0.90
ν_{ar}	Air kinematic viscosity (T _{ref} =30°C)	1.608 x 10 ⁻⁵ m ² /s
ϵ_{abs}	Absorber emissivity	0.12
Q_u	Total Useful heat gain in collectors	80.0 - 86.6 kW _{th}
Q_{inc}	Total Solar radiation incident in collectors	137.0 - 147.0 kW _{th}

Source: Author elaboration

4. Results and Discussion

The optimal steady state analysis, after simulating hourly conditions of the proposed Solar Organic Rankine Cycle (S-ORC) showed very interesting results regarding the performance of the R-123 as a suitable fluid for small-scale operations. The power consumed in both pumps, which had an assumed 80% of isentropic efficiency, was of about 1.31 kW or 8.7% of gross electricity output (Table 2).

The cycle performs very well with the use of a recuperator. Calculations demonstrated that not only its existence decreases the amount of heat addition to working fluid in heat exchangers, but it also decreases the condenser load as well. Results shows a good performance in terms of ORC's overall efficiency of 17.29%, being:

$$\eta_s = \frac{\dot{W}_{TV} - \dot{W}_{Pumps}}{\dot{Q}_H} \quad (17)$$

Table 2 – ORC and HTF Systems overall operational parameters

Parameter	Value
Net Turbine Output (W_{TV})	15 kW
$W_{PUMP, R123}$	360 W
$W_{PUMP, THERMAL OIL}$	960 W
Thermal Fluid specific heat	1.953kJ/kgK
Mass Flow Rate of organic fluid R-123	0.375kg/s
Mass Flow Rate of thermal oil Dowherm	0.675 kg/s
Double Pipe Heat Exchanger (Steam Generator) Pressure	1,200 kPa (12bar)
Steam Generator (Annulus) Inlet Temp	38°C
Steam Generator (Annulus) Exit Temp	120°C
Steam Generator (Tubeside) Inlet Temp	189°C
Steam Generator (Tubeside) Exit Temp	125°C
Calculated Net Transfer Rate at Double Pipe Heat Exchanger	79.80 kW _{th}
Inner Diameter of Annulus Tube	42.16 mm
Outer Diameter of Annulus Tube	52.50 mm
Tubeside Heat Transfer Calculated Coefficient	1,183 W/m ² -K
Annulus Heat Transfer Calculated Coefficient	1,641 W/m ² -K
Number of passes at Steam Generator	12
Calculated tube length per pass	3.3 m
Turbine Exit Temperature	42°C
Recuperator ΔT_{Temp} Shell	14°C
Recuperator ΔT_{Temp} Tubes	10°C
Condensator Exit Temp	28°C
Condensator Exit Pressure	101.3 kPa

Source: Author elaboration

A thermodynamics approach has been employed to demonstrate how the variables involved in the functioning of the ORC under analysis behave, along with a general analysis of the equipment and their role in the overall performance. This issue could be further developed to facilitate a more profound understanding of the sizing of heat exchangers. From the data and equations considered in calculations and through an energy balance, a number of 60 PTCs in series, divided into four parallel rows of 15 collectors each, was obtained.

Constitutive equations for the problem were solved with equipment parameters and operating conditions, along with other fluid data, to provide an arrangement that can deliver the necessary electricity to supply one or more houses, a local school and a small clinic in remote areas, with a total daily demand of about 160 kWh.

As illustrated in Figures 5 and 6, the thermodynamic behaviour of the cycle is delineated in both diagrams: Temperature versus Entropy and Pressure versus Enthalpy. It is evident that the fluid undergoes

an expansion from a state of slight superheating to a state of low pressure and low temperature. However, the organic fluid persists in the superheated steam state, a condition that is advantageous for the turbine, as it mitigates losses due to cavitation (see Fig. 3).

This inherent property of organic fluids in ORCs is particularly advantageous to turbine performance and longevity. Furthermore, the incorporation of a heat recuperator between the turbine outlet and the condenser entrance has enhanced the temperature of the pressurised liquid exiting the condensate pump, thereby optimising the cycle. The high observed efficiency of ORCs is attributed to the favourable operation conditions, which extract the majority of the thermodynamic performance of the refrigerant without the necessity of adding a super heater, which is costly and requires additional maintenance and controlling.

FIGURE 3. R-123 Temperature versus Entropy Diagram
Source: Author elaboration within R-123 curves

As well noted by [8], one of the main advantages of using an organic fluid as working fluid of the Rankine cycle is the slope of the saturated vapor entropy line in the T-s diagram as can be seen above. Fluids with this behaviour are usually known as dry fluids, since no condensation occurs in the expansion process inside the steam turbine, making its lifetime higher and increasing performance (Refer to Fig. 4).

The overnight capital cost C_0 is measured in dollars per installed kilowatt (\$/kWe) and includes the direct costs (i.e. materials and equipment) and the owner's costs (i.e. land preparation, project development, financing, etc) of the system. Capital recovery factor (CRF) is a fraction calculated as described below. Fixed Operation and Maintenance (O&M) costs in dollars per kilowatt-year and variable O&M costs in dollars per kilowatt-hour (\$/kWh).

The estimated C_0 for the small-sized S-ORC facility was around \$2,003 per kWe, considering that land for the site is available without costs (public land in remote location). That for an assumed fixed O&M costs ($f_{CO\&M}$) of \$80/kWe-yr and variable O&M costs of \$0.02/kWh ($v_{CO\&M}$), a capacity factor (CF) of 33% Calculations of $sLCOE_{sol}$ were performed with a nominal discount rate of $i=11.0\%$ and the following:

$$CRF = \frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1} \quad (18)$$

$$sLCOE_{sol} = \frac{C_0 \frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1} + f_{CO\&M}}{8760 \cdot CF} + v_{CO\&M} \quad (19)$$

FIGURE 4. R-123 Pressure versus Enthalpy Diagram
Source: Author elaboration within R-123 curves [25]

The financial outlay required for the acquisition of the Twin Turbine 15kW is €16,950, with freight charges (FOB). The total approximate capital expenditure (CAPEX) is \$30,045, which encompasses the costs of the turbine, pumps, PTC, pipelines, recuperator, heat exchanger, start-up battery, and miscellaneous equipment (see Table 3).

Table 3 – General equipment estimated costs based on [12, 23, 24, 30, 31 and commercial price quotations]

Equipment	Price (US\$)
Turbine cost	\$18,645
Pumps cost	\$1,000
PTC Steel Sheets Cost (A304 polished 0.5 mm)	\$6,000
Pipeline & Others	\$1,300
Double Pipe Heat exchanger x recuperator	\$3,100
Total cost of investment	\$30,045

Economic calculations encompassed all the necessary equipment to initiate the system, in conjunction with a modest 1kW battery set, to facilitate equipment operation during the initiation phase and to store electricity during periods of sunlight deficiency. The project was analysed through the utilisation of the forecast cash flow method, incorporating an electricity price estimate of approximately \$0.18/kWh to project savings (with federal and state taxes included).

The calculated present value of the project's cash flow for electricity savings (growth at 3.0% p.a.) and total costs (growth at 1.0% p.a.), 5% depreciation rate with no final value (scrap) was \$22,285, with an IRR=22.7% in 20 years. The calculated levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) was \$0.135/kWh for the same 20-year period, without considering the additional thermal heat provided, which is a significant benefit when compared to PV panels alone.

The optimal ratio of the S-ORC's power output to the usable capacity of the battery storage in kWh is 1:1. Consequently, the implementation of a 15kW battery storage system is recommended to enhance the security of the electricity system and to stabilise feed-in curves or battery discharges during periods of high demand. However, this would have a detrimental effect on the preliminary estimates of CAPEX.

Currently, the sLCOE of small rooftop photovoltaic systems with battery storage ranges usually from \$0.1/kWh to 0.216/kWh [26, 27]. This wide cost range is due to the large price difference of the various battery systems, which means that the S-ORC system is operating within an acceptable price range for a pilot unit.

5. Conclusion

The data for the cycle examined in this study has also been instrumental in validating that local sustainable generation using SORCs in regions with elevated solar irradiation can be a viable alternative to photovoltaic panels. Given the range of methodologies available for certain calculations, numerous parameters can be adjusted to align with the specific case under study, and the consideration of alternative fluids is also permitted.

The performance of small-scale S-ORCs in remote off-grid areas and locations with intense solar radiation has been demonstrated. The results indicate that the S-ORC in study exhibits a satisfactory level of efficiency, with an overall efficiency of 17.29%, which is noteworthy when considering that the majority of contemporary

regular crystalline silicon photovoltaic (PV) cells operate at efficiencies ranging from 13.0% to 19.0%.

While it is acknowledged that the S-ORC would necessitate more proactive and potentially corrective maintenance, the system's deployment in standalone modules for both thermal and solar sides would facilitate its integration as a viable alternative to crystalline silicon PV cells in certain scenarios.

Furthermore, the calculated sLCOE of \$0.135/kWh, over the lifetime of the project and its estimated six-year payback period with electricity savings, renders it highly competitive when compared to the price range of small rooftop PV systems, particularly in light of the additional thermal heat provided.

The chosen organic fluid, either R-123 or HFO-1233zd(E), is supposed to be condensed in an air condenser to avoid unnecessary water consumption, but if there is water available or the need to attend thermal demand at a hotel or facility for example, this would imply that condensate rejected heat could be used for this purpose. As such, the use of an additional 0.5 HP water pump in the project, would deliver around 27.0 l/min of heated water at 57 °C.

It is imperative to acknowledge the accessibility of all requisite equipment at commercial scales, thereby enabling the seamless assembly of the entire system at the designated location. This can be facilitated through the utilisation of national equipment such as pipelines, valves, temperature controllers, thermal storage tanks, fluid gear pumps, and other associated components.

PTC systems have demonstrated a long operational life of 20-30 years or more when proper maintenance is in place, which makes them a durable investment. This is in contrast to PV panels, which have been observed to undergo a gradual efficiency loss over time. A key advantage of PTC systems is their versatility, they can be dispatched to the desired region in modules for assembly and set up for operation in the final location. Also, adapted equipment can easily replace the chosen ones, which makes it also flexible to punctual changes and enhancements.

To achieve a comprehensive understanding of the system's parameters, such as temperature control and fluctuations over time, particularly in instances of partial sun blockage, the implementation of a field test is essential. Additionally, a practical assessment of the start-up procedures is required to determine the necessary battery backup, ensuring the operational integrity of the system until it can transition to a permanent regime.

The analysis of the produced data indicates that Organic Rankine Solar facilities, employing low-impact organic derivatives emerge as compelling and cost-effective alternatives for electricity provision and secondary thermal demand fulfilment in off-grid areas and remote locations with intense solar radiation.

Data availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. This manuscript is a preprint; comments and suggestions are welcome.

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* Email: Fernando.leal@usp.br